

Studies on the bioremediation potential of glyphosate by the green saltwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris*

Estudios sobre el potencial de biorremediación del glifosato por la microalga verde de agua salada *Chlorella vulgaris*

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ABSTRACT

Glyphosate (N-(phosphonomethyl)-glycine) $C_3H_8NO_5P$ is a major ingredient in various herbicides used in global agricultural practices. However, the financial benefits of its application come with concerns for human health and ecological preservation, highlighting the necessity to quantify and monitor glyphosate pollution. In this study we improved a protocol for residual glyphosate quantification in alkaline media based on the reaction between glyphosate and chromogenic reagent ninhydrin when exposed to a solution of sodium molybdate at 85-95°C, which produces a Ruhemann's purple product with a VIS maximum absorption at a wavelength of 570nm. Furthermore, we screened green saltwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* as a bioremediation agent using an acute toxicity test, concentration gradient exposure, and by measuring its ability to remove glyphosate from BG11 liquid media. The glyphosate calibration curve was linear for aliquots ranging at 2.5-20mg/L with a correlation coefficient of 0.991 and a limit of detection and quantification of 0.057mg/L and 0.191mg/L, respectively. *C. vulgaris* grew in BG11 medium with glyphosate concentrations ≤ 7.50 mg/L, while the Lethal Dosage 50% value was estimated at 3.97mg/L with a 95% confidence interval. Finally, our findings demonstrated that *C. vulgaris* successfully reduced glyphosate concentrations from an alkaline medium by 47.71% within a period of eight days. Our findings indicate that while *C. vulgaris* couldn't decrease glyphosate concentrations to EPA standards of 0.7mg/L, it does show potential as a bioremediation agent. Thus, further research is required towards its real-world application.

Keywords:

Saltwater microalgae, *Chlorella vulgaris*, Glyphosate assay, Spectrophotometry

RESUMEN

El glifosato (N-(fosfonometil)-glicina) $C_3H_8NO_5P$ es el ingrediente principal en varios herbicidas utilizados en las prácticas agrícolas a nivel mundial. Sin embargo, los beneficios financieros de su aplicación vienen con la preocupación por la salud humana y la preservación ecológica,

lo que destaca la necesidad de cuantificar y monitorear la contaminación por glifosato. En este estudio mejoramos un protocolo para la cuantificación de glifosato residual en medios alcalinos basado en la reacción entre el glifosato y el reactivo cromogénico ninhidrina cuando se exponen a una solución de molibdato de sodio a 85-95°C, que produce un producto púrpura de Ruhemann con una absorción máxima VIS a una longitud de onda de 570nm. Además, evaluamos la microalga verde de agua salada *Chlorella vulgaris* como agente de biorremediación mediante una prueba de toxicidad aguda, exposición a gradiente de concentración y midiendo su capacidad para eliminar el glifosato de los medios líquidos BG11. La curva de calibración de glifosato fue lineal para alícuotas que oscilaron entre 2.5 y 20 mg/L con un coeficiente de correlación de 0,991 y un límite de detección y cuantificación de 0.057 mg/L y 0.191 mg/L, respectivamente. *C. vulgaris* creció en medio BG11 con concentraciones de glifosato ≤ 7.50 mg/l, mientras que el valor de la dosis letal al 50 % se estimó en 3.97 mg/l con un intervalo de confianza del 95 %. Finalmente, nuestros hallazgos demostraron que *C. vulgaris* redujo con éxito las concentraciones de glifosato de un medio alcalino en un 47.71 % en un período de ocho días. Nuestros hallazgos indican que *C. vulgaris* no pudo disminuir las concentraciones de glifosato a los estándares de la EPA de 0.7 mg/L, pero así aun muestra potencial como agente de biorremediación. Por lo tanto, se requiere más investigación para su aplicación en el mundo real.

Palabras clave:

Microalga de agua salada, *Chlorella vulgaris*, Glifosato, Espectrofotometria

Introduction

In 1971, Monsanto Co. chemist Dr. John E. Franz, discovered a compound he would later call Glyphosate (N-(phosphonomethyl)-glycine) $C_3H_8NO_5P$. Glyphosate is a broad-spectrum, non-selective, and post-emergence type of organophosphorus herbicide widely used to control annual and perennial plant growth. By 1974 glyphosate was released commercially, quickly becoming one of the active ingredients of a well-established herbicide known as Roundup® (Bhaskara, 2006). A few decades later, in 2000, Monsanto's exclusive use of the patent on glyphosate ended. This termination triggered changes in the production industries, as competing companies started integrating this ingredient into their brand of herbicides. The high demand for glyphosate-based herbicides and the ever-growing agricultural practices has led to the introduction of large quantities of glyphosate and many other chemical surfactants onto large portions of land in agriculturally active nations worldwide. This expansion has raised concerns regarding glyphosate's impact or ill effects

on human health and exposed ecosystems. Glyphosate has been shown to display multiple adverse effects, including but not limited to teratogenesis, carcinogenesis, mutagenesis, and detrimental effects in prenatal development (Sharma et al., 2012). According to the Journal of Immunotoxicology: glyphosate and glyphosate-based products have been found to alter the hormone metabolism, induce abnormalities like severe cranial and skeletal malformations, and affect the growth/development of nerve cells in mammals and humans (Peillex et al., 2020). These growing concerns have led to the investigation and monitoring of glyphosate in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, as well as the study of its removal through the application of bioremediation practices.

The United States Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA) has found that people with short-term and long-term exposure to glyphosate at levels above the Maximum Contaminant Levels (MCLs) are potentially at risk of developing moderate to severe medical conditions with profound effects on their health and well-being (US EPA, 2018). Previous

publications revealed that short-term exposure to glyphosate could cause congestion of the lungs and increased breathing rates. In contrast, long-term exposure could induce kidney damage, negatively influence child development, and adversely affect reproduction (Bai, 2016). The effects of glyphosate exposure also extend to aquatic ecosystems and the community of organisms that inhabit them (USDA, 1997). Roundup® is found to be moderately toxic to freshwater fish, slightly harmful for aquatic invertebrates, non-toxic for amphibians, and not toxic at post-spray levels for a variety of algae species from British Columbia Forest streams which use glyphosate as a source of phosphorous for algal growth (USDA, 1997). Additional studies regarding the exposure of an array of shrimp species to glyphosate concentrations of 0.70mg/L showed impairment or slow movement in all stages within their life cycle (Mensah et al., 2011), diminished cellular and muscular growth (Frontera et al., 2012), and a reduction in overall growth with increased lipidic peroxidation (Mensah et al., 2012).

Growing agricultural practices have led to higher demand and use of herbicides like Roundup, whose service provides higher crop yields, while also leading to the accumulation or transport of residual chemical compounds via soil leaching, runoff, and deposition into nearby terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Mensah et al., 2011). As of the 1990s, nearly 20 million acres of land within US territories have been treated with over 18.70 million pounds of glyphosate yearly (US EPA, 1993) and as of 2013, Monsanto acquired more than 500 acres of land in PR (Santiago et al., 2016). The high accumulation of pesticides and herbicides in marine ecosystems can harm the health, wellness, and natural dynamic of organisms exposed to them (Frontera et al., 2012). Long-term exposure to pesticides can poison or kill off affected communities. At the same time, surviving organisms suffer from the bioaccumulation of hazardous compounds, which can disturb an ecosystem's nutrient cycle and food web (Bai, 2016). As the detrimen-

tal effects of herbicides in aquatic ecosystems are being monitored for studies on the behavioral dynamics of exposed macroinvertebrates and freshwater communities, the integration of a new bioremediation practice is on the rise. The use of green saltwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* (Beijerinck, 1890) as a treatment to remove or reduce various pesticides, inorganic compounds, and hazardous chemicals from aquatic resources has proven the potential of microalgae-based bioremediation to be a viable, economical, and effective option for research in bioremediation of marine ecosystems for (Baglieri et al., 2016; Liu, 2017; Calderón-Delgado, 2019).

The influence of Roundup exposure on the growth rate of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* can be observed with an acute toxicity test where batches of *C. vulgaris* would be exposed to different concentrations of glyphosate (zero to 30mg/L) over a period of one week. The goals here were to determine the glyphosate tolerance threshold of *C. vulgaris*, see how microalgae cell production is affected across the glyphosate gradient, and decide an ideal initial glyphosate concentration in a solution to observe how a microalgae-based treatment removes glyphosate from a liquid media. Similar toxicity tests have been performed on freshwater shrimp, like *Cardina nilotica* (Roux, 1833), where the shrimp were exposed to different concentrations of Roundup, and deaths were used to estimate the herbicide's median lethal concentration (LC50) as the direct effect of the glyphosate exposure (Mensah et al., 2011).

Previous publications have developed easy, economical, and reproducible methods for quantifying glyphosate from natural water samples and neutral mediums using specially designed chemical assays and simple spectrophotometry techniques (Bhaskara et al., 2006). Two of these assays are based on the reaction between glyphosate and ninhydrin in the presence of sodium molybdate in neutral aqueous media while exposed to temperatures of 100°C for 3-5 minutes (Bhaskara et al., 2006) or 85-95°C for 12 minutes (Tzaskos et

al., 2012), which produces a Ruhemann's purple product with a stability time of 10 hours and a maximum visible absorbance at 570nm. The glyphosate concentrations were determined using calibration curve concentration ranges from 0.1-3.5mg/L and 4-14mg/L, respectively (Bhaskara et al., 2006; Tzaskos et al., 2012).

For this study, we implemented the same glyphosate assay. We attempt to create a calibration curve with a concentration range of zero to 30mg/L to determine the residual glyphosate concentrations of environmental water and liquid media samples, which were prepared to analyze glyphosate removal or reduction using green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* as a bioremediation agent. Since Puerto Rico doesn't have specialized stations to directly monitor glyphosate concentrations in its freshwater streams, it limits the potential study of its impact on stream ecology within the region. This protocol could serve as a possible glyphosate model to record, observe, and analyze the effect of glyphosate fluctuation in local freshwater streams.

The U.S. EPA, the Brazilian National Environmental Council Resolution 357/05, and the Ministry of Health Statute 518/MS/04 have established the permissible levels of glyphosate in natural waters and aquatic resources at 0.70mg/L, 0.067mg/L and 0.50mg/L respectively (Marques et al., 2009). The U.S. EPA also established the Maximum Contaminant Level (MCLs) for protection against acute effects as 3µg/L and 12µg/L for chronic effects (USGS, 2019). Anything higher can put people at risk of severe health issues, adversely affect the aquatic communities within the exposed ecosystem, and affect the ecological services they provide for the environment. Therefore, it is of great interest to monitor the water quality of streams and aquatic resources regarding residual glyphosate concentrations sourced from Roundup® Weed & Grass Killer and other herbicide brands that utilize glyphosate as their active ingredients.

In this study, we evaluated methods of glyphosate quantification and its removal from liquid media through three objectives.

We proposed improving residual glyphosate quantification methods for the first objective by applying simple chemical assays and spectrophotometry techniques. Colorimetric assays can be sensitive to various conditions such as pH, temperature, and other chemical substances (Askim et al., 2017; Felton et al., 2018). Thanks to detailed observations and analysis of the developments in glyphosate quantification efforts by (Bhaskara et al., 2006; Tzaskos et al., 2012), we predicted that it would be possible to expand the previously observed glyphosate quantification range to that of zero to 30mg/L.

The second objective involved studying the impact of glyphosate exposure on the proliferation of green saltwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* across a glyphosate concentration gradient of zero to 30mg/L. Previous studies have revealed an effective bioremediation potential of green microalgae *C. vulgaris* in removing heavy metals, industrial dyes, complex compounds, and organic pollutants from both water and soil (Reno et al., 2015; Nie et al., 2019; Chin et al., 2020). Due to its reputable nature as a bioremediation agent, we chose *C. vulgaris* as our organism of interest. We subjected it to a glyphosate toxicity test against a concentration gradient of zero to 30mg/L and analyzed its response to herbicide stressors. We also ran an acute toxicity test to determine the Lethal Dosage 50% (LD50) value. We hypothesized that the effect of glyphosate on *C. vulgaris* cell proliferation in BG11 liquid media would be more significant at higher concentrations than at lower concentrations. Here we aimed to prove that the mean cell count of *C. vulgaris* will not be equal when cultivated at different glyphosate concentrations ($\mu\text{O} \neq \mu\text{I} \neq \mu\text{N}$). We also expected the microalgae to show signs of growth at concentrations between zero and ten mg/L of glyphosate, with the LD50 value falling around 5.0mg/L.

For our third objective, we observed if *C. vulgaris* had any possible application as a bioremediation agent capable of removing or reducing glyphosate from BG11 liquid me-

dia. After determining *C. vulgaris*' glyphosate tolerance range and LD50 value, we evaluated its bioremediation potential in removing of glyphosate from BG11 liquid media. We hypothesized that *C. vulgaris* microalgae in glyphosate-spiked BG11 liquid medium (treatment group) would decrease glyphosate herbicide concentrations at higher rates than in glyphosate-spiked BG11 liquid medium where the microalgae were not added (control). We aimed to prove that the mean glyphosate concentration is not equal between the control and the *C. vulgaris* treatment throughout the seven days of incubation ($\mu\text{O Control} \neq \mu\text{I Treatment}$).

Experimental design

Primary reagents, stock solutions, and media

The stock solutions for this project were prepared with filter-sterilized deionized Millipore water. Ninhydrin and Sodium molybdate dihydrate were used to make 5% stock solutions for the glyphosate assay and spectrophotometric analysis. The glyphosate used for this project was sourced from a 1.04L Roundup® Weed & Grass Killer product comprised of 18% Glyphosate (isopropylamine salt), 0.73% Diquat dibromide, and 81.27% of other active ingredients. That being said, the Roundup® Weed & Grass Killer product was diluted to prepare the 500mg/L glyphosate stock that would be used for the glyphosate calibration curve, toxicity test and chemical reduction assay. Next, glassware, general stock solutions, and liquid media were sterilized via autoclave at 121°C for 30 minutes. Finally, the glyphosate stock solution was filtered into a sterile one-liter glass bottle with a 0.45µm membrane filter kit and laboratory-grade vacuum pump.

A few studies call for dF2 media or Bold Basal Medium (BBM) when cultivating *C. vulgaris* (Blair et al., 2014). Still, after careful consideration and observation, we found that minor adjustments to the standard BG11 liquid media recipe displayed a better potential for sample cultivation and spectrophotometry analysis

when compared to dF2 media and Bold Basal Medium (BBM). Furthermore, by applying minor adjustments in the BG11 liquid media recipe, we could provide saltwater microalgae like *C. vulgaris* with more favorable conditions to grow and decrease the necessary incubation period by half. Therefore, for this experiment, we implemented a modified recipe for BG11 media for *C. vulgaris* microalgae culturing, a glyphosate toxicity test, and the spectrophotometry-based glyphosate reduction assay.

The stock solutions needed for the BG11 media are listed in (Table 1). We prepared batches of BG11 media by placing one liter of dH2O in two-liter glass bottles and adding 1.0mL of each stock solution in order from 1 to 6 as seen in (Table 1), 35g of NaCl (when working with saltwater samples) and 1.5mg of NaNO₃. The BG11 media was homogenized after each stock solution (or reagent) was added using a magnetic pill with

a magnetic stirring hot plate. After homogenizing the media, the pH was brought to 8.00 and autoclaved at 121°C for 30 minutes.

Table 1. Component stock solutions for BG11 liquid medium recipe. Authors.

No.	Stock solutions	Components	Quantity (mg/500mL)
1	K-Pi	K ₂ HPO ₄	15.25
2	MgSO ₄	MgSO ₄ *7H ₂ O	37.50
3	Na ₂ CO ₃	Na ₂ CO ₃	10.00
4	CaCl ₂	CaCl ₂ *2H ₂ O	18.00
5	Fe-Chelate	Fe(III) Citrate	3.00
		Citric Acid	3.00
		Na ₂ Mg*EDTA or Na ₂ EDTA	0.50
		H ₃ BO ₃	1.43
		MnCl ₂ *4H ₂ O	0.90
6	Micro-elements	ZnSO ₄ *7H ₂ O	0.11
		Na ₂ MoO ₄ *2H ₂ O	0.195
		CuSO ₄ *5H ₂ O	0.04
		Co(NO ₃) ₂ *6H ₂ O	0.025
7	NaNO ₃	NaNO ₃	84.75

Note: each stock was sterilized via the use of an autoclave and allowed to cool at room temperature before being used.

For microalgae plating, an additional batch of BG11 agar was prepared by adding 15g of bacteriological agar from Fisher Scientific to one liter of BG11 medium with a pH of 8.00 before autoclaving at 121°C for 30 minutes.

Once the medium was sterilized and reached a temperature of 50-60°C, it was plated onto 100x25mm Petri dishes. Subcultures were prepared in triplicates with the quadrant streaking technique and incubated with standard illumination for one week before being stored in a 4°C fridge as preserved stocks.

Culturing *Chlorella vulgaris* in BG11 medium

We obtained a stock of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* from the University of Texas in Arizona (UTEX) and cultured triplicate samples for later use. First, we diluted our apportion of the *C. vulgaris* stock in a three-step (1:10) serial dilution and used 1000 μ L of our (1:1000) dilution to inoculate four milliliters of BG11 medium for a 1:5 culture. The five milliliters of BG11 liquid culture were placed in a 20mL glass test tube with a breathable lid and incubated under aerated conditions at 25°C, 25-30rpm, and exposed to artificial blue/white light for a period of seven days. This produced five milliliters of the primary *C. vulgaris* liquid culture. Secondly, the five milliliters of the liquid culture were then subjected to a 5:25 or 5:50 scale-up, where the same five milliliters were used to inoculate 20 or 45mL of fresh BG11 medium and incubated under similar conditions as stated before (under aerated conditions at 25°C, at 25-30rpm and exposed to artificial blue/white light for a period of seven days). This produced 25-50mL of a *C. vulgaris* liquid culture, serving as inoculum for the glyphosate toxicity tests and the herbicide removal assay treatment. Using general microscopy, it was possible to observe samples of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Microscopy imagery of green saltwater microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* stock subculture (UTEX). Authors.

Developing a calibration curve for glyphosate analyzes

Previous articles stipulate that glyphosate in neutral aqueous media can be detected via spectrophotometry when using a glyphosate-based reaction to produce Ruhemann's purple product (Bhaskara et al., 2006). This reaction can be seen in (Figure 2) when glyphosate ($C_3H_8NO_5P$) is allowed to react with chromogenic reagent Ninhydrin ($C_9H_6O_4$) while in the presence of the reaction catalyst sodium molybdate (Na_2MoO_4) at temperatures of 85-95°C for 12 minutes, which produces a Ruhemann's purple (Tzaskos et al., 2012). Following this concept, we attempted to create a calibration curve for glyphosate ranging from zero to 30mg/L.

We started by preparing a 500mg/L working solution of glyphosate, a 5% ninhydrin stock, and a 5% sodium molybdate stock solution (all filter-sterilized or autoclaved). Once the working solutions were ready, we transferred a portion of glyphosate stock into 5mL test tubes to make aliquots ranging from zero to 30mg/L. Then we added 500 μ L of the 5% ninhydrin stock and 500 μ L of the sodium molybdate stock to each aliquot. Solutions were mixed via vortex for 10-15 seconds and exposed to a 90°C hot bath for 12 minutes (briefly vortexed every 4 minutes). The resulting aliquots produced a purple hue, "Ruhemann's purple" product visible at a wavelength of 570nm and a stability time of ten hours (Tzaskos et al., 2012).

We allowed the aliquots to cool down until they reached a room temperature of 25°C before they could be used. Then, the aliquots were transferred into individual 15mL falcon tubes, and distilled or deionized water was added until each aliquot solution reached a final volume of 5mL. Once topped off to 5mL, we transferred 1,000 μ L of each aliquot solution into their corresponding spectrophotometry well and observed their unique absorbance within a wavelength range of 250-750nm. Ruhemann's purple product was expected to

have a maximum VIS absorption at 570nm according to standard protocols established by (Bhaskara et al., 2006) and (Tzaskos et al., 2012).

Once the absorbance data were procured for each aliquot, we then prepared two graphs: a standard wavelength graph for - absorbance vs. wavelength (250-750nm) - and a calibration curve for - max absorbance (at 570nm) vs. glyphosate concentration (mg/L) - respectively. The calibration curve was used to establish a reliable y-intercept and R2 value to calculate residual glyphosate from media and environmental water samples (where we hoped the R2 value would be between 0.80 and 0.99 for quality assurance). Next, we used an RStudio program to design a linear regression model between maximum absorbance values and glyphosate aliquot concentrations to determine if the data was a good fit for glyphosate quantification as suggested by (Lilja et al., 2022). We then validated the calibration curve by interpreting

the linear regression model summary, y-intercept, R2 value, and the residual behavior plot for our data (Normal Q-Q and Residual vs. Fitted). Finally, we calculated the limits of detection (LOD), limits of quantification (LOQ), and prediction error percentage. The LOD was defined as the lowest analyte concentration that can be detected but not necessarily quantified. In contrast, the LOQ was defined as the lowest analyte concentration that can be quantified in a sample with acceptable accuracy and precision (Brito et al., 2003)

$$\text{Limit of Detection (LOD)} = 3.3(Sy/S) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Limit of Quantification (LOQ)} = 10(Sy/S) \quad (2)$$

Where Sy is the standard deviation of the calibration curve, and S is the slope of the calibration curve (Tzaskos et al., 2012).

Glyphosate Toxicity: *C. vulgaris* growth vs. Herbicide Gradient Exposure

For the glyphosate concentration gradient, we used the BG11 media to prepare the standard dilutions at different glyphosate con-

centrations, as seen in (Table 2). We designed six to twelve replicas of a (1:10) inoculation of each standard dilution from the concentration gradient. We took two transparent six-well plates per glyphosate concentration of interest. We added 9mL of their respective standard dilution into each well and then inoculated them with 1.0mL of a (1:10) dilution of the *C. vulgaris* cultured stock $\sim 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ cells/ μ L. Inoculated samples were then incubated under aerated conditions, with transparent/breathable microplate sealing film, in a shaker at 25°C and 25-30rpm for a 12-hour cycle of repetitive exposure to artificial blue/white light for four to ten days of observation. On day four, we observed if there were any preliminary visual changes in *C. vulgaris* cell growth within the BG11 liquid cultures.

After the seven-day incubation period, we performed a microalgae cell count using a standard hemocytometer and microscope. Next, we performed a (1:10) dilution for each replica and counted the number of cells within 100 μ L. Dilutions were done using BG11 media rather than distilled water to avoid cell lysis. Finally, we graphed the data for glyphosate concentrations and the average number of *C. vulgaris* cells to find the relationship between *C. vulgaris*' microalgae growth in BG11 media when exposed to different glyphosate concentrations. This graph was designed to interpret the response of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* when exposed to different glyphosate concentrations, as prepared in (Table 2). As such, the graph was to be titled "*C. vulgaris* microalgae cell counts vs. Glyphosate concentration (mg/L)."

We ran a simple One-Way ANOVA and a Tukey HSD test to interpret whether or not the cellular proliferation of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* was affected by glyphosate exposure and if its impact is significant. First, we performed the One-Way ANOVA to interpret if the effects of different glyphosate concentrations on cell count for *C. vulgaris* were significant and verified said significance with a Tukey HSD (honestly significant difference test). The One-Way ANOVA was used to de-

termine if there was a statistically significant difference between the mean cell count of two or more groups of glyphosate concentrations. In contrast, the Tukey HSD test determined which of the glyphosate concentration groups had significantly different mean cell counts from each other.

Figure 2 Chemical reaction pathway of Glyphosate and Ninhydrin while in the presence of Sodium molybdate to produce Ruhemann's purple product as described by (Bhaskara et al., 2006)

A tolerance threshold refers to the maximum amount of a substance that an organism, sample or population can tolerate without exhibiting adverse effects. This works toward identifying and mitigating risks in public health and ecological preservation efforts (Lappi et al., 2018). Using the graphed data for - cell count vs. glyphosate concentration (mg/L) - we aimed to study the visible glyphosate tolerance range of *C. vulgaris* microalgae within the observed glyphosate concentration gradient of zero to 30mg/L. In addition to determining *C. vulgaris'* glyphosate tolerance range, we also wanted to determine the mean lethal dose value of glyphosate for *C. vulgaris* microalgae by performing an acute toxicity test (LD50 evaluation) with Minitab PC software. An acute toxicity test is a type of experiment that determines the level of toxicity of a substance by measuring the dosage of a said substance that would cause harmful effects on a test subject or population through short-term exposure... the LD50 test is a type of acute toxicity test that refers to the amount of a substance required to kill off 50% of a population or test subjects within a given period (Lappi et al., 2018). Both the LD50 test and graphed data - cell count vs. glyphosate concentration (mg/L) - were then used to de-

termine the ideal starting concentration for the glyphosate reduction assay.

No	Concentration (ppm)	Glyphosate stock (mL)	BG11 media (mL)	Final volume (mL)
1	30.00	3.00	47.00	50.00
2	27.50	2.75	47.25	50.00
3	25.00	2.50	47.50	50.00
4	22.50	2.25	47.75	50.00
5	20.00	2.00	48.00	50.00
6	17.50	1.75	48.25	50.00
7	15.00	1.50	48.50	50.00
8	12.50	1.25	48.75	50.00
9	10.00	1.00	49.00	50.00
10	7.50	0.75	49.25	50.00
11	5.00	0.50	49.50	50.00
12	2.50	0.25	49.75	50.00
13	0.00	0.00	50.00	50.00

Note: We used a glyphosate stock with a concentration of 500ppm (500mg/L) to create a glyphosate concentration gradient with glyphosate standards ranging from zero to 30.00ppm (or mg/L), which were later inoculated with 1.0mL of a (1:10) dilution of the *C. vulgaris* cultured stock $\sim 1.0 \times 10^{-2}$ cells/ μ L.

Herbicide removal: *C. vulgaris* treatment in media with glyphosate

According to previous articles, microalgae *C. vulgaris* has effectively reduced or removed a wide range of chemicals and pesticides in media (Baglieri et al., 2016; Liu, 2017). Therefore, it is expected that *C. vulgaris* will also reduce glyphosate concentrations from Roundup in the BG11 media. Thus, we prepared a standard calibration curve to estimate and monitor glyphosate concentrations in BG11 media treated with *C. vulgaris* microalgae.

This section aimed to test *C. vulgaris'* ability to reduce glyphosate concentrations from Roundup® Weed & Grass Killer in spiked BG11 liquid media. First, we selected the initial glyphosate concentration to measure the rate of herbicide removal from BG11 media as a result of seven-day microalgae treatment with *C. vulgaris*. The initial concentration of glyphosate used in this step was determined from the analysis performed in the previous section, with the toxicity test, where we studied the effects of herbicide exposure on the cellular proliferation of *C. vulgaris*. Understan-

ding the glyphosate tolerance threshold for *C. vulgaris* microalgae when exposed to Roundup® Weed & Grass Killer would tell us which concentrations would be tolerable and which starting concentration would be ideal for the herbicide removal test.

Initially, it was believed that we could start the herbicide reduction assay with an initial concentration of 20mg/L. Still, after carefully analyzing *C. vulgaris'* response to a glyphosate gradient, we estimated that an ideal starting concentration for glyphosate was between 5.00 and 7.50mg/L. With this in mind, we prepared a batch of BG11 liquid media with a glyphosate concentration of 7.00mg/L to serve as the medium for both the control and experimental groups. We designed fifty 10mL replicas of untreated BG11 medium to be used as a control group (not inoculated with *C. vulgaris*) and another fifty 10mL replicas of BG11 liquid medium, with the same starting concentration as the control group, which were inoculated with *C. vulgaris* microalgae stock as a treatment (these would be the experimental treatment group). The replicas within the experimental treatment group had been inoculated with 1.0mL of a $\sim 1.94 \times 10^2$ mg/L of *C. vulgaris* culture stock, as suggested by previous papers (Baglieri et al., 2016). After the inoculation, we incubated samples under standard aerated conditions, in a 25°C shaker, at 25-30rpm, and under a 12-hour cycle of repetitive exposure to artificial blue/white light for a total of seven days of observation.

The protocol used to process and measure glyphosate in BG11 liquid media samples was similar to the ones implemented by both (Bhaskara et al., 2006; Tzaskos et al., 2012), with a few minor alterations due to the use of the BG11 medium (pH 8.00 \pm 0.02) as the liquid base and the *C. vulgaris* microalgae cell culture procured as the treatment.

We took out five 10mL replicas from the control and treatment groups daily. Each replica was adequately sealed and vortexed thoroughly for 10-20 seconds before being centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The supernatants were filtered through individual

0.45um membrane filters and transferred into separate 50mL test tubes while the microalgae pellets were discarded. These supernatants were evaporated from 10mL to 1mL by subjecting them to a 45-50°C hot bath (instead of completely evaporating the supernatant and resuspending the dry residues in deionized Millipore water). The reduced supernatants were then individually transferred onto new 5.0mL Eppendorf tubes, where we added 500 μ L of 5% Ninhydrin and 500 μ L of 5% sodium molybdate. Each solution was mixed rigorously and then heated in a hot bath at 85-95 °C for 12 minutes (vortexed for 5 seconds every 4 minutes). After the heat treatment, we allowed the solutions to cool down until they reached room temperature (25°C), and the visible color of the samples had a visible purple hue (*Ruhemann's purple product*). After each solution reached room temperature, we filled the 5.0mL Eppendorf tubes up to five milliliters with deionized Millipore water. Finally, one milliliter of each sample was transferred onto a clean spectrophotometer well for spectrophotometric analysis.

Using a spectrophotometer, we observed each sample within a wavelength range of 200-800nm and measured the maximum absorbance of each solution at the wavelength of interest for glyphosate (570nm). Using the calibration curve from the previous steps, the max absorbance data, and the y-intercept formula, we attempted to distinguish the concentration of glyphosate for the corresponding replicas of the experimental treatment and the control group. The concentration data from the replicas were used to determine the average daily glyphosate concentration for the control group, the experimental treatment, and graphing purposes. The control was a basis for comparing the experimental treatment using *C. vulgaris*. It allowed us to observe if the glyphosate herbicide degrades on its own overtime when suspended in BG11 media.

The experimental treatment was used to show if *C. vulgaris* reduces or removes herbicides from BG11 media over a seven-day observation period. Statistical analyses were

performed to determine if the difference in herbicide concentration between the control and the treatment was significant throughout the seven-day observation period. The statistical analysis was done using simple Two-way ANOVA and a Tuckey HSD on R-studio. The Two-Way ANOVA interpreted the considerable difference between the control and experimental treatment concentrations and the mean difference for both groups per day. In contrast, the Turkey HSD test was used to verify said significance. One of the purposes of this experiment was to distinguish if the use of *C. vulgaris* successfully removes glyphosate from liquid media, which could further our understanding of glyphosate and increase the application of microalgae-based bioremediation in science when attempting to mitigate the contamination of aquatic ecosystems.

Results

Developing a calibration curve for glyphosate analyzes

Our efforts to improve upon the existing limitations of standard glyphosate quantification protocols with an analytic calibration curve were based on the reaction between Glyphosate and Ninhydrin while undergoing heat treatment in a solution with Sodium molybdate to produce a Ruhemns' purple product with a maximum absorbance at 570nm as in (Figure 2). First, we collected Ruhemann's purple absorbance data from the glyphosate aliquots ranging from zero to 30mg/L and graphed the absorbance curves in (Figure 3). Then, we created a glyphosate calibration curve using the maximum absorbance value at the 570nm wavelength and the corresponding glyphosate concentrations of each aliquot (Figure 4).

However, the glyphosate calibration curve in (Figure 4) was limited to a concentration range of (2.5-20mg/L), which exhibited good linear behavior, a y-intercept formula of ($y = 0.041x - 0.0725$), and a coefficient of determination (R^2) value of (0.991). Using an RStudio linear regression model of our data (Table 5), we were able to confirm these values,

as well as a slope between absorbance and glyphosate concentrations as (0.0411079) with a p-value of (< 0.001). In addition, the linear regression model also reported data correlation with multiple R^2 values of (0.992) and an adjusted R^2 value of (0.9917) under an (F-statistic of 2737; DF 1,22; p-value: < 0.001) at a 95% confidence interval.

The residual behavior plots can be appreciated in (Figure 5). Here the residual vs. fitted plot (Figure 5-1) show evidence of linearity for most of the absorbance data with a few deviations via outliers for aliquot points 10mg/L, 12.50mg/L, and 17.50mg/L, which coincides with the prediction error percentage results higher than $\pm 4.00\%$ from (Table 5). In the Normal Q-Q plot (Figure 5-2) we can see that our data does indeed follow a linear trend except for the 2.50mg/L and 12.50mg/L aliquot points on the graph. We could assume that the proximity to the lower limit of the calibration curve can influence a level of error in linearity for points near 2.50mg/L and the level of deviation for the outliers in the 12.50mg/L aliquot points. However, the curve's systematic sensitivity or limitation values were estimated at (LOD 0.057mg/L; LOQ 0.191mg/L) using the RStudio linear regression model results in (Table 3). Previous publications establish similar LOD/LOQ values within a glyphosate calibration range of four to 14mg/L, from which we infer that our calibration curve data could be a good fit.

While the points in the calibration curve (Figure 4) displayed good linear behavior, we could observe that points at 10mg/L, 12.50mg/L, and 17.50mg/L deviated from the expected response values set forth by the trendline and its data points.

With this in mind, we performed a three-point estimate of prediction error percentages for the curve points at 5mg/L, 10mg/L, and 15mg/L of the glyphosate calibration curve, as seen in (Table 4). For the first point (I), whose expected concentration value was that of 5mg/L, we calculated a glyphosate concentration of (5.1279mg/L) with a prediction error percentage of (2.56%). In contrast

Figure 3 Absorbance curves for glyphosate assay aliquots (zero to 20.00mg/L). Authors.

Figure 4 Standard calibration curve for glyphosate assay aliquots (zero to 20mg/L).

Figure 5-1 RStudio Calibration Curve Residual data analysis: Residual vs. Fitted Plot

Figure 5-2 RStudio Calibration Curve Residual data analysis: Normal Q-Q Plot

to the second point (II), where the expected concentration value was that of 10mg/L, we calculated a glyphosate concentration of (9.5069mg/L) with a prediction error percentage of (-4.93%). Finally, for the third point (III), with an expected concentration value that of 15mg/L, we calculated a glyphosate concentration of (15.0854mg/L) with a prediction error percentage of (0.57%). Coincidentally, for the aliquot with the expected concentration of 17.50mg/L, we obtained a calculated response value of (18.2641mg/L) with a prediction error percentage of (4.37%) as in (Table 5).

Under standard calibration curve protocols acceptable levels of prediction error percentages fall between ($\pm 5\%$). Therefore, we could assume that the calibration curve's linear behavior and correlation coefficient (R^2) in (Figure 4) are good indicators that the y-intercept formula should work to estimate residual glyphosate concentrations. However, results from our estimate of prediction error percentages in (Table 4) indicate that the calibration curve's minimum and maximum prediction error percentages range from (-4.93% to 4.37%) and for concentrations at 2.50m/L the error was estimated at 20.79%, as seen in (Table 5).

Hence, we could assume that our curve and its points fall within an acceptable error level except for the 2.50mg/L point, which is understandable given its proximity to the lower limit of the curve and the LOD/LQD values.

Table 3 RStudio linear regression model analysis: Glyphosate calibration curve. Authors.

Call: lm(formula = Absorbance ~ Concentration, data = Calibration)				
Coefficients:				
	Estimate	Standard Error	t-value	Pr(> t)
(Intercept)	-0.07246	0.00991	7.306	< 0.001
Concentration	0.04110	0.00785	52.320	< 0.001
Residual standard error: 0.02205 on 22 degrees of freedom				
Multiple R-squared: 0.992, Adjusted R-squared: 0.9917				
F-statistic: 2737 on 1 and 22 DF, p-value: < 0.001				

When formulating the y-intercept formula ($y = mx - b$) and R-square value (R^2) for the glyphosate calibration curve using an RStudio linear regression model; we observe that

R-square value (R2) is interpreted as the Adjusted R-squared, the intercept (b) as the estimate of intercept, the slope (m) as the estimate of concentration, the max absorbance at 570nm wavelength as (y), and the calculated residual glyphosate concentration as (x).

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Table 4 RStudio: Three-point prediction error percentages for the glyphosate calibration curve.

Calibration Parameters	Calibration Curve Points of Interest		
	I	II	III
Point of interest			
Expected Concentration (mg/L)	5.00	10.00	15.00
Number of Points on Curve (n)	8	8	8
Lower Point - Concentration (mg/L)	2.50	2.50	2.50
Upper Point - Concentration (mg/L)	20.00	20.00	20.00
Coefficient of determination (R ²)	0.992	0.992	0.992
Slope (m)	0.0411079	0.0411079	0.0411079
Intercept (b)	-0.072464	-0.072464	-0.072464
Calculated Concentration (mg/L)	5.1279	9.5069	15.0854
Standard Deviation (σ)	0.1334	0.0487	0.0612
Prediction Error Percentage (%)	2.56%	-4.93%	0.57%

Note: A three-point estimation of prediction error percentage for aliquot concentrations - 5mg/L, 10mg/L, and 15mg/L - would serve to determine if the aliquots within the glyphosate calibration curve fall within an acceptable prediction error that is lower than 5%.

Table 5 RStudio: Glyphosate calibration curve prediction percentage error (%). Authors.

Expected Concentration (mg/L)	Average Absorbance Values	Average Calculated Concentration (mg/L)	Prediction Error Percentage (%)
2.50	0.052	3.01963775	20.79%
5.00	0.138	5.127910531	2.56%
7.50	0.230	7.349705693	-2.00%
10.00	0.310	9.50691239	-4.93%
12.50	0.417	11.89870966	-4.81%
15.00	0.548	15.08544505	0.57%
17.50	0.678	18.26407171	4.37%
20.00	0.748	19.95068993	-0.25%

A full-scale point estimation of the prediction error percentage for aliquot concentrations from 2.50mg/L, and 20.00mg/L would further serve to determine if all the aliquot points within the glyphosate calibration curve fall within an acceptable prediction error that is lower than 5%.

Under standard calibration curve protocols acceptable levels of prediction error percentages fall between (±5%). Therefore, we could assume that the calibration curve's linear behavior and correlation coefficient (R2) in (Figure 4) are good indicators that the y-intercept formula should work to estimate residual glyphosate concentrations. However, results from our estimate of prediction error percentages in (Table 4) indicate that the calibration curve's minimum and maximum prediction error percentages range from (-4.93% to 4.37%) and for concentrations at 2.50m/L the error was estimated at 20.79%, as seen in (Table 5).

Glyphosate toxicity: *C. vulgaris* growth vs. herbicide gradient exposure

Before we could test the bioremediation potential of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* in the herbicide removal assay, we first had to distinguish the extent of the microalgae's tolerance range for glyphosate concentrations within the established standard solutions with zero to 30mg/L of glyphosate, as

well as the Lethal Dosage 50% value (LD₅₀). It was possible to visually appreciate the negative impact that glyphosate exposure had on the cellular proliferation of *C. vulgaris* microalgae in a cell count per glyphosate concentration boxplot, as seen in (Figure 6). However, it was only possible to count microalgae cell proliferation in BG11 liquid media when glyphosate concentrations fell between zero and 7.50mg/L as seen in (Table 6; Figure 6). Hence, we noticed that when *C. vulgaris* grew in BG11 liquid media without the presence of glyphosate, the cell count yielded an average of 1565.83 cells/uL (Min 1430; Max 1720; SD 89.39), while BG11 liquid media with 7.50mg/L of glyphosate yielded an average of 277.50 cells/uL (Min 190; Max 360; SD 55.62) in contrast to when the BG11 liquid media had glyphosate concentrations higher than 7.50mg/L where no cells could be found or quantified for *C. vulgaris* microalgae.

Table 6 Toxicity Test: *Chlorella vulgaris* cell count data per glyphosate concentration summary. Authors.

Concentration	n	Average	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation
0.00mg/L	12	1565.83	1430	1720	89.39
0.50mg/L	12	1382.50	1311	1553	65.80
1.00mg/L	12	1272.47	1210	1362	48.27
2.50mg/L	12	1075	973	1177	68.29
5.00mg/L	12	910	742	1048	91.25
7.50mg/L	12	277.50	190	360	55.62

Figure 6 *Chlorella vulgaris* cell growth response to glyphosate exposure (zero-30.00mg/L). Authors.

We tested the significance in the variance of cell count per concentration by performing a simple One-Way ANOVA (F-value 486.12; p-value < 0.0001) as seen in (Table 7) and followed up with a post hoc Tukey HSD test (with a repeated adjusted p-value < 0.005 for all comparisons) to verify the difference in cell count. The One-Way ANOVA and the

post hoc Tukey HSD results reveal that the average cell count values for *C. vulgaris* microalgae significantly differed between their respective glyphosate concentrations (0.0mg/L, 0.5mg/L, 1.0mg/L, 2.5mg/L, 5.0mg/L and 7.5mg/L). Finally, the Probit acute toxicity test (LD50 test) we ran on the Minitab computer program revealed that the LD50 value of glyphosate for green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* was estimated to be at 3.97mg/L (with a 95% confidence interval) given the designed standards of observation (Figure 7).

With these findings, we have enough evidence to deny the null hypothesis and accept that the mean microalgae cell count of *C. vulgaris* was not equal when cultivated at different glyphosate concentrations ($\mu_0 \neq \mu_1 \neq \mu_n$). Therefore, the estimated ideal starting concentration for glyphosate in media for the herbicide reduction assay was set between (5-7.5mg/L).

Table 7 One-Way ANOVA: Glyphosate toxicity test for *Chlorella vulgaris*. Authors.

Analysis of Variance Table					
Response: Cells	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F-value	Pr(>F)
Concentration	5	124500.00	24900.00	486.12	< 0.0001
Residuals	66	3381	51.2		

Figure 7 Minitab Probit Analysis (LD50 Test): *C. vulgaris* mortality vs. glyphosate exposure. Authors.

Herbicide removal: *C. vulgaris* treatment in media with glyphosate

Once we determined the glyphosate tolerance threshold for green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris*, we performed the glyphosate

herbicide removal assay. First, we prepared batches of BG11 liquid media with a pH of 8.00 (± 0.02) and an initial glyphosate concentration of 7mg/L. We then compared the daily changes in glyphosate readings between a control group without *C. vulgaris* as a microalgae treatment, and the experimental treatment group inoculated with microalgae. This comparison can be visually appreciated in (Table 8; Figure 8), where we see the daily average glyphosate level per group and their corresponding standard deviation from the mean. Hence, the overall microalgae treatment with *C. vulgaris* displayed a 47.71% decrease in glyphosate concentration, while the control's overall glyphosate concentration slightly decreased by only 2.75% within eight days of observation.

Table 8 Glyphosate reduction assay daily concentration means (conc) & standard deviation (sd). Authors.

No.	Day	Control mean (mg/L)	Treatment mean (mg/L)	Control sd	Treatment sd
1	0	7.095	7.076	0.153	0.095
2	1	6.988	6.720	0.121	0.105
3	2	7.051	6.120	0.078	0.105
4	3	6.910	5.207	0.162	0.170
5	4	7.017	4.383	0.110	0.262
6	5	6.915	4.090	0.147	0.147
7	6	6.773	3.876	0.094	0.127
8	7	6.900	3.705	0.115	0.224

Figure 8 Glyphosate reduction assay with *Chlorella vulgaris* treatment and control. Authors.

Table 9 Two-Way ANOVA: Glyphosate reduction assay. Authors.

	Df	Analysis of Variance Table		F-value	Pr(>F)
		Sum Sq.	Mean Sq.		
Type	1	69.63	69.63	9646.80	< 0.0001
Day	7	37.62	5.37	744.50	< 0.0001
Type:Day	7	29.73	4.25	588.30	< 0.0001
Residuals	64	0.46	0.001		

"Type" refers to the observed groups within the glyphosate reduction assay (Control & Microalgae treatment), "Day" to the eight-day period of observation, and "Type:Day" to the interaction between group and time factors in relation to the response variable (glyphosate concentration).

We tested the significance in the variance of the average glyphosate concentrations between the two groups (control and microalgae treatment), as well as the significance in glyphosate variance per day, and interaction factor of groups per day (groups~days), by performing a simple Two-Way repeated measures ANOVA as seen in (Table 9). The results of Two-Way repeated measures ANOVA variance in means for the average glyphosate concentrations between the two groups (control and treatment) revealed an (F-value of 9646.80; p-value < 0.0001). When testing the significance in glyphosate variance per - day - results showed an (F-value of 744.50; p-value < 0.0001). We also found that the interaction between - groups and days - in response to glyphosate concentration variance yielded an (F-value of 588.30; p-value < 0.0001).

The Two-Way repeated measures ANOVA found that the average glyphosate concentration values significantly differed between their respective experimental groups (control and microalgae treatment). It also showed that the average glyphosate concentrations were significantly different across the days of observation. The treatment manifested a significant drop in glyphosate concentration for the microalgae treatment over time. The Two-Way repeated measures ANOVA also yielded substantial differences in glyphosate concentrations within the interaction of (groups~days). We see that the glyphosate concentration value did not manifest equally between the (control and the microalgae treatment). With these findings, we have enough evidence to deny the null hypothesis and accept that the mean glyphosate concentration was not equal between the control and the *C. vulgaris* treatment throughout the seven days of incubation (μ_0 Control \neq μ_1 Treatment).

Discussion

Developing a calibration curve for glyphosate analyzes

Glyphosate is a nonvolatile phosphonate methyl derivative of the amino acid glycine. It

has one primary amino group and three ionizable acidic sites that do not undergo photochemical degradation (Kanissery et al., 2019) unless subjected to extensively controlled conditions within a lab setting (Chen et al., 2007). It is also known for the controversy and the debate behind its carcinogenic classification, which could be

attributed to the weight placed on the results of human epidemiological studies (Gillezeau et al., 2019). And though it is a financially rewarding herbicide within agricultural practices (Mensah et al., 2013) it is recognized for its adverse effects on human health and its persistence in the environment, particularly in water and soil (Padilla et al., 2018).

With specialized stations to directly monitor glyphosate concentrations in its freshwater streams, Puerto Rico would be safe from unknown exposure to residual glyphosate from agricultural or industrial practices. Our study designed its glyphosate quantification protocol based on chemical assays established in previous works (Bhaskara et al., 2006; Tzaskos et al., 2012) while considering influential factors that might affect the resulting absorbance values within our protocol - base medium, pH, temperature treatments, intermittent light exposure, and extraction process - as suggested by (Marques et al., 2009; Rashid et al., 2022). Analysis of glyphosate absorbance and concentration data was subjected to an RStudio linear regression model as established in works by (Barwick, 2003; Carlberg, 2016).

The glyphosate chemical assay by (Tzaskos et al., 2012) recommends using neutral pH-based media. Still, careful testing showed that BG11 alkaline media (pH 8.00) worked just as well in culturing our microalgae of interest - *C. vulgaris* - and towards quantifying glyphosate in media, with little to no significant signs of interference. Our findings show that the conditions set forth by our glyphosate assay protocol yielded viable data for designing a calibration curve of good linear behavior with an agreeable or acceptable prediction error percentage of ($\leq \pm 5.00\%$). However, we ex-

clude values below the 2.50mg/L point of the calibration curve due to its proximity from the established limits of the curve as reported by the (LOD; LOQ) values.

Glyphosate toxicity: *C. vulgaris* growth vs. herbicide gradient exposure

Aside from developing herbicide quantification methods, our study also focused on the glyphosate reduction potential of green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris*. Due to the researched application of green microalgae *C. vulgaris* in the removal of synthetic dyes, heavy metal, and complex compounds in the media and freshwater samples (Calderón et al., 2019; Nie et al., 2019; Chin et al., 2020), we expected that it would also be successful in the removal of glyphosate sourced from Roundup® Weed & Grass Killer. However, before testing *C. vulgaris* glyphosate removal potential, it was essential to first assess its tolerance threshold for glyphosate with both a simple gradient exposure analysis and an acute toxicity test as suggested in works by (Liu et al., 2017).

Visual results showed that green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* grew when exposed to different glyphosate concentrations. The analysis of a One-Way ANOVA with a post hoc Tukey HSD test (Maziti et al., 2018) revealed that the cellular proliferation of the microalgae could be considered significantly different per the observed concentrations. While the microalgae didn't grow to the expected concentration of 20mg/L, it did show signs of cell proliferation up to a concentration of 7.50mg/L with a lethal dosage 50% value of (LD50 3.97mg/L). This analysis allowed us to observe the effects of glyphosate exposure in *C. vulgaris* when subjected to different standard concentrations of glyphosate as established in our protocol. According to the US EPA, glyphosate is regulated as a primary drinking water standard and further states that the Maximum Contaminant Level (MCL) and Maximum Contaminant Level Goal (MCLG) are both set at 0.7mg/L (Pontius, 2003). From these findings, we can infer that green

saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* can grow past the established glyphosate regulations levels and could be used to test further its ability to remove glyphosate from alkaline media and freshwater samples.

Herbicide removal: *C. vulgaris* treatment in media with glyphosate

The annual estimate of glyphosate herbicide usage within an agricultural setting in the United States is approximately 280 million pounds of glyphosate applied to 298 million acres of land (US EPA, 2018). Therefore, following the assumption that Puerto Rico uses similar practices, it would be considered essential to have the means to monitor and mitigate glyphosate pollution around local freshwater streams. However, before we could implement green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* as a bioremediation agent for glyphosate reduction, we first had to test its efficiency in glyphosate removal within a lab setting. With this in mind, we implemented a glyphosate reduction assay in BG11 alkaline liquid media (pH 8.00) while using a standard repeated measure Two-Way ANOVA as a basis for analysis, as suggested in (Maziti et al., 2018).

We modeled the glyphosate reduction experiment with two comparable groups (control and microalgae treatment). The control represented BG11 liquid media with an expected glyphosate concentration of 7.00mg/L. It worked as a basis for comparison with the experimental treatment group and showed how stable glyphosate behaved within eight days of observation. The experimental treatment represented BG11 liquid media with an expected glyphosate concentration of 7.00mg/L and a considerable *C. vulgaris* microalgae inoculum concentration similar to works by (Baglieri et al., 2016). In addition, the treatment observed significant changes in glyphosate concentrations occurred in contrast to the control group, which was similar to the designed method in previous works (Nie et al., 2019).

The glyphosate herbicide removal assay compared the glyphosate concentrations

from the control and experimental groups throughout eight days of observation. The Two-Way repeated measure ANOVA revealed that the changes in glyphosate concentration between the experimental treatment and control groups were significant, as well as for the differences observed between days and the interacting glyphosate values between groups and days of observation (groups--days). This substantial change in glyphosate concentration could constitute a success within the glyphosate removal assay. Furthermore, the overall level of glyphosate reduction induced by green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* treatment was estimated at approximately 47.71% when comparing treatment group average concentrations between the first and final day of observation. In contrast, previous publications used a microalgae-bacterium consortium cultivated between *Chlorella protothecoides* and *Pseudomonas stutzeri* within a standard photobioreactor with increasing glyphosate concentrations (5-50mg/L), which was capable of reducing glyphosate concentrations by about 53% and 79% during long-term operations of water treatment (Borella et al., 2022).

A limitation in our glyphosate herbicide removal assay was establishing a short period of observation for the microalgae treatment to remove glyphosate from media. Under industrial standards for pesticide removal, *C. vulgaris* wasn't able to reduce the glyphosate concentration to well within EPA standards under the established eight-day period of observation but was in fact capable of reducing the glyphosate concentration from alkaline medium by close to 50%. It is recommended that in future projects we observe how *C. vulgaris* behaves when exposed to glyphosate for an extended period of time and see if it is indeed capable of decreasing the overall concentration to or below the EPA standard of 0.7mg/L for glyphosate in freshwater streams and drinking water. Thus, our findings lead us to assume that *C. vulgaris* could have potential as a bioremediation agent for future glyphosate bioremediation studies.

Conclusion

Protocol adjustments allowed us to develop improvements on existing calibration curve systems for analyzing and quantifying residual glyphosates with chemical assays and general spectrophotometry. Our quantification efforts resulted from careful alterations in the standard protocol factors, such as changes in the base liquid media used, the medium's pH, intermittent light exposure in incubation, limited sample purification, and the glyphosate assay heat treatment duration. We also determined a significant glyphosate tolerance range and lethal dosage values for green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* by subjecting the obtained data to a One-Way ANOVA and an acute toxicity test (LD₅₀ Probit test) on RStudio and Minitab programs respectively. Finally, the herbicide removal analysis using *C. vulgaris* as a treatment to remove glyphosate from BG11 liquid media reflected a significant difference in concentration between control and treatment over time, which leads us to assume that green saltwater microalgae *C. vulgaris* could be considered as a potential bioremediation agent in future studies regarding glyphosate pollution. However, understanding the extent of *C. vulgaris*' bioremediation potential and its real-world application toward glyphosate pollution mitigation in freshwater streams warrants further research to be performed.

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